

STEREOCHEMISTRY OF HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART I.
CONFORMATIONAL ANALYSIS OF AJMALINE, AJMALIDINE,
SERPININE AND RAUWOLFINE-THE DIHYDRO-
INDOLE ALKALOIDS OF RAUWOLFIA

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Stereochemical formulation of some of the Rauwolfia alkaloids has been discussed from their conformational analysis.

From *Rauwolfia* genus eight indoline bases, viz., ajmaline, isoajmaline, ajmalidine, serpinine (= tetraphyllicine), rauwolfine, rauvomitorine, semperforine (Schlitter and Furlenmeier, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 36, 996) and vomalidine (Hofmann and Frey, *ibid.*, 1957, 40, 1866), have been isolated. Although much work has been done for elucidation of their structures, very little attention has been paid to clarify their stereochemical formulation. It is therefore intended to take up this study. Ajmaline (Ia) (Chatterjee, Pakrashi and Werner, *Fortschr. Chem. Org. Natur.*, 1956, 13, 369); Woodward, *Angew. Chem.*, 1956, 68, 13; Robinson, *ibid.*, 1957, 69, 40), ajmalidine (Ib) (Djerassi *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 88, 1259), serpinine (Ic) and rauwolfine (II) (Bose, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 374; 1958, 35, 72; Chatterjee *et al.*, *loc. cit.*)-these four indoline alkaloids have been selected for the purpose.

[I]

[II]

- a. Ajmaline: $R_1 = C_2H_5$; $R_2 = OH$; $R_3 = OH$.
b. Ajmalidine: $R_1 = C_2H_5$; $R_2 = (>C=O)$; $R_3 = OH$.
c. Serpinine: $R_1 = (=CH.CH_3)$; $R_2 = OH$; $R_3 = H$.

An insight into the configuration of these indoline compounds has been possible from their conformational analysis.

For the construction of the appropriate molecular models of the above bases, the following procedure is necessary:

(1). The piperidine ring C by analogy with *cyclohexane* (Barton and Cookson, *Quart. Rev.*, 1956, 10, 44) is to be assigned chair configuration.

(2). The juncture at C/D constituting a reduced pyridocoline system must be considered as *cis* and not *trans*. It has been observed that *trans*-fusion brings C and D approximately in the same plane, separating C₅ (in ring C) and C₁₅ (in ring D) wide apart. This arrangement prevents the C₅-C₁₅ linkage through a single carbon atom at 16 which is essential for constituting the six-membered ring F (I). But if the juncture is *cis*, rings C and D become non-planar, and a boat configuration for ring D in such a case ensures the desirable proximity of C₅ and C₁₅ to construct the ring F.

(3). The alternate chair conformation for ring D₂ has been examined. It creates the same difficulty, i. e., C₅ and C₁₅ linkage becomes impossible as they recede far from each other.

Following these conditions, an accurate scale molecular model has been assembled and it reveals the following important stereochemical features of ajmaline, ajmalidine and serpinine molecules :

(i). The ring juncture at B/C is *trans*, through the equatorial bonds of C₂ and C₇ (referred with respect to ring C). B and C cannot be *cis*-fused by any means because this arrangement would not permit the construction of the model as would be evidenced in the sequel. *Cis*-fusion of rings B and C would involve linkage through the axial bond of C₂ and equatorial bond of C₇. The pentacyclic ring E involving C₅, C₈, C₇ demands the axial bonds of C₅ and C₇ (*cis* orientation). Hence, the axial bond of C₇ being unavailable for fusion of B and C rings, a *cis*-fusion of these two rings is possible only through the equatorial bond of C₇ and the axial one of C₂. Such a conformation would be unstable as (a) they involve heavy substitution on adjacent diaxial bonds and (b) the hydrogen at C₂ would be subjected to considerable non-bonded interaction with rings D and E.

(ii). The rings C and D are also *cis*-locked through the axial bond of C₂ and equatorial bond of N₄ (with respect to ring C).

(iii). C₃-H is equatorial and has α -orientation.

(iv). D and F possess boat conformation.

(v). D and F constitute a bicyclic ring system with N₄ and C₁₅ at the bridgehead positions.

(6). C₃-H and C₁₅-H are *cis*, these orientations being considered in relation to ring D.

It needs mention in this connection that the conformation of serpinine, which bears an exocyclic ethylidene group at C₂₀, does not differ from that of ajmaline and ajmalidine, having an ethyl group at the same carbon atom.

As regards the orientation of -OH at carbon 17, nothing definite can be assessed because the configuration of any five-membered ring is still to be defined.

In rauwolfanine (II), the basic ring skeleton is almost the same as that of ajmaline, ajmalidine and serpinine with the exception that the ring E in (II) is six-membered representing a pyran nucleus. The stereochemical requirements at C₅ and C₁₅

necessitate that this pyran ring should also assume a boat form. C₆ and C₁₆ are adjacent carbon atoms of the ring E, and their equatorial and axial bonds are *cis*-oriented. This arrangement results only in a boat and not a chair form for this ring, for adjacent equatorial and axial bonds are *trans* in any chair configuration.

[III]

[IV]

The stereoconfigurations, (III) and (IV), thus established for ajmaline, ajmalidine, serpinine and rauwolfiine, can offer an explanation for (a) and (b).

(a) *The failure of indoline-N-methyl to produce stable salts with acids.*—According to electronic interpretation, indoline -N.CH₃ would be appreciably basic in character and should produce stable salts with mineral acids, which is not the case. The model shows that the rings D and F contribute appreciable steric hindrance towards the approach of the attacking reagent. Should they approach at all, and react with indoline-N.CH₃, the resulting products would be highly strained, unstable and would decompose. This adduces the most logical explanation of the suppressed basic character of indoline-N.CH₃ occurring in dihydroindole alkaloids of *Rauwolfia* genus.

(b). *Abnormal carbinolamine reaction (observed in ajmaline).*—Owing to the symmetry of adjacent rings D and F, both being in the boat configuration, the conformationally preferred orientation of any substituent in these rings is difficult to be stated with precision. Any of the substituents, which is in the equatorial conformation with respect to ring D, is as well axially oriented with respect to ring F and *vice-versa*. Substituents in these rings, in whatever conformation they may exist, are considerably hindered owing to (1 : 2H), (1 : 4H) and (1 : 5H) interactions.

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Received December 6, 1957.

